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CHOCOLATE, OR AN INDIAN DRINKE: THE FIRST ENGLISH TRANSLATION OF A SPANISH CHOCOLATE TREATISE

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the first English translation of Colmenero's *Curioso Tratado de la Naturaleza y Calidad del Chocolate* (1631). The analysis of the English version, *Chocolate, or an Indian Drinke*, by James Wadsworth is carried out from a qualitative perspective, paying special attention to the translated strategies deployed. The research reveals that Wadsworth will chiefly use procedures such as the preservation of indigenous words and extension, as well as other techniques to a lesser extent.

KEYWORDS: Colmenero de Ledesma, *Tratado sobre el chocolate*, James Wadsworth, *Chocolate, or an Indian Drinke*, Translation strategies

STRESZCZENIE

Celem niniejszego artykułu było zbadanie pierwszego angielskiego tłumaczenia traktatu autorstwa Colmenero pt. *Curioso Tratado de la Naturaleza y Calidad del Chocolate* (1631). Analiza angielskiej wersji *Chocolate, or an Indian Drinke*, autorstwa Jamesa Wadswortha, została przeprowadzona z perspektywy jakościowej, zwracając szczególną uwagę na zastosowane strategie tłumaczeniowe. Z badań wynika, że Wadsworth stosował przede wszystkim takie zabiegi jak zachowanie rodzimych słów i rozszerzenie, a także, w mniejszym stopniu, inne techniki tłumaczeniowe.

SŁOWA KLUCZOWE: Colmenero de Ledesma, Traktat o czekoladzie, James Wadsworth, *Chocolate, or an Indian Drinke*, strategie tłumaczeniowe

INTRODUCTION

Christopher Columbus encountered the cacao on his fourth voyage to the Americas in 1502. He and his crew captured a canoe containing cacao beans near Guanaja, a small island off mainland Honduras. They did not pay much attention to the seeds, referred to as *almonds*, since they were not aware of the real value of cacao to native American people. Subsequently, chocolate did not make any impact on Spanish society until Hernán Cortés got in contact with Mexican Aztecs in 1519.

No one knows exactly when cacao first reached Spain. Some give credit for the introduction to Hernán Cortés and a Spanish friar who went with him, Fray Aguilar, who is said to have sent cacao to the abbot of the *Monasterio de Piedra* (Stone

Monastery), Fray Antonio de Álvaro. The monastery is said to be one of the first places in Europe to cook this new stuff. Regarding the introduction of chocolate at the Spanish court, Coe and Coe (1996: 130) claim that it happened in 1544 through some Maya nobles brought by Dominican friars to meet Prince Philip. It was not until 1585 that transoceanic commerce in cacao beans became regular into Europe. The fashion of tasting the American drink was expanded through Spain and finally exported to France, Italy and Britain, where “the first chocolate drinking was established in London in 1657” (Beckett 2008: 2). In fact, chocolate is present in British society since then, as public and private documents attest. Thus, *The Indian Nectar* by Stubbe was written in English and published in 1662. In the same vein, the Earl of Sandwich’s journal, written in 1668, records a recipe along with other issues related to the production of chocolate (Loveman 2013: 27).

Native Americans had already discovered the medical properties of cacao and used it extensively for different ailments. Thus, the *Florentine Codex* (1590), compiled by Bernardino de Sahagún, “described that chocolate was normally taken in compound form combined with herbs and flowers to treat digestive disorders, fevers and a wide variety of other complaints” (Albala 2007: 56). In 1591 Juan de Cárdenas in *Problemas y Secretos Maravillosos de las Indias (Problems and Wonderful Secrets of the Indies)* warns that chocolate, if green, is harmful for digestion, but, if roasted, gets people fat and helps digestion (Rivero-Ruiz 2002: 298–299). Nonetheless, Colmenero was not aware of the existence of those references which did not deal with chocolate exclusively, although he knew a study by Bartolomé Marradón published in 1618: *Del Chocolate: Diálogo entre un Médico, un Indio y un Burgués (On Chocolate: A dialogue between a Physician, an Indian and a Bourgeois)*, mentioned in Colmenero’s first chapter (1631:299).

Colmenero was himself a graduated physician from the University of Osuna. He published a book in Seville in 1622 entitled *Apologia Chirurgical* and sometime later he travelled to America. As a result of his direct contact with chocolate, Colmenero wrote his *Curioso Tratado de la Naturaleza y Calidad del Chocolate*, which was published in Madrid in 1631. The treatise, devoted entirely to the medical qualities of chocolate, gained popularity, and was translated into diverse languages, including Latin, French and English.

The first English translation, *A Curious Treatise of the Nature and Quality of Chocolate* appeared in 1640 under the pseudonym of Diego de Vades-forte¹. It was reprinted under the translator’s real name, James Wadsworth, with a new title: *Chocolate, or an Indian Drinke* (1652). No wonder Wadsworth was an ideal candidate to render Colmenero’s original work into English, since he was well

¹ James Wadsworth puns upon the translation of his first name, whereby James is adapted as Diego. It is common knowledge that several proper names are related etymologically giving rise to different versions in Spanish. Thus, the translator could have chosen between Jaime (closer to its English version), Jacobo, Yago, Santiago or Diego. James Wadsworth selects the latter, among all the different options.

acquainted with the Spanish language and culture. Wadsworth's father was appointed chaplain to Sir Charles Cornwallis on his embassy to Spain in 1605. Subsequently, he departed for Spain that year. His wife and children joined him in Andalusia in 1610. According to Loomie (2004), his son James "attended schools in Spain until 1618, when he entered the Jesuit English College at St Omer in Artois. [...] Later in 1623 Wadsworth was asked to be an interpreter for courtiers in Prince Charles's entourage in Madrid". After several years in Spain and Flanders, James Wadsworth eventually returned to England in 1625, where he produced the translation of Colmenero's work.

This article discusses some of the choices made by James Wadsworth and explores the translation strategies² followed in the first rendering in English of Colmenero's *Curioso Tratado de la Naturaleza y Calidad del Chocolate*. This study aims to contribute to the analysis of medical texts and their translations in the Early Modern English period.

COLMENERO'S *CURIOSO TRATADO DE LA NATURALEZA Y CALIDAD DEL CHOCOLATE*

Apart from the authors referred to above, there were other contemporary writers who mentioned chocolate, such as Agustín de Farfán in his *Tratado Breve de Medicina* (1592), José de Acosta in *Historia Natural y Moral de las Indias* in 1604 and in 1624, Santiago de Valverde Turices in *Un Discurso del Chocolate* (Dillinger *et al.* 2000: 2060, 2064), but there is no evidence of Colmenero's consultation of them. The text under study here is, thus, one of the first credited medical treatises written in Spanish about chocolate and probably the most widely disseminated, thanks to its translation into other languages.

The Spanish text has a lengthy title, which reads *Curioso tratado de la naturaleza y calidad del chocolate, dividido en cuatro puntos. En el primero se trata, que sea Chocolate; y que calidad tenga el Cacao, y los demas ingredientes. En el segundo, se trata la calidad que resulta de todos ellos. En el tercero se trata el modo de hazerlo, y de quantas maneras se toma en las Indias, y qual dellas es la mas saludable. El vltimo punto trata de la cantidad, y como se ha de tomar, y en que tiempo, y que personas*. Afterwards, it is mentioned that it was written by Antonio Colmenero de Ledesma, physician and surgeon at Ecija city.

The prefatory items of the Spanish volume include a permission to print the treatise signed by the King, the fees or taxes, the allowance of Doctor Melchor de Lara and the testimonial of Doctor Juan de Mena. All these sections are followed by

² There is no agreement on the use of the denomination *translation techniques* and *translation strategies*, although some scholars distinguish between them (see Hurtado-Albir 2011: 271ff.). In this article both labels are used indistinctively.

the preface dedicated to the reader. In the latter, Colmenero highlights the fact that chocolate is not only drunk in the Indies, but also in Spain, Italy and Flanders, especially at court. He also mentions that nobody, but the physician from Marchena, referring to Bartolomé Marradón, has ever written about chocolate and then, he proceeds to explain the structure of the treatise in four points.

The first point deals with the qualities of cacao, clearly establishing that the treatise follows the prevalent theory of humours governing the health of human beings. The tenets of this theory go back to classic physicians like Hippocrates and Galen, whereby sickness is the result of the imbalance of the four humours in the human body. Since medical practice was still based on these principles, discoverers of herbs in the New World struggled to categorise and define them according to the humoral theory. After this, he offers a recipe for chocolate. The second point is about the mixture of the simples that are contained in the recipe. The third point is about the *modus faciendi* and how it is prepared in the Indies and finally the author deals with the quantity, how, when and by whom it should be consumed.

A CURIOUS TREATISE OF THE NATURE AND QUALITY OF CHOCOLATE AND CHOCOLATE, OR AN INDIAN DRINKE

The text printed in London in 1640 under the pseudonym of Diego de Vadesfortes starts with a literal translation of the first part of the Spanish original title: *A Curious Treatise of the Nature and Quality of Chocolate*. It claims to have been written in Spanish by Antonio Colmenero, “Doctor in Physicke and Chirurgery”, but ignores the author’s birth town. This omission probably responds to the translator’s desire to avoid irrelevant material. Then, it is stated that it was translated in English by Don Diego de Vades-forte.

The prefatory items include a letter to “the Right Honourable Edward Lord Viscount Conway and Killultah; Baron of Ragley; Lord Marshall of the Army, and Privy Counsellour of Ireland; and one of the Counsell of Warre to his Maiesty of Great Brittain”. In this letter, the translator pretends to be a foreigner, “who hath newly learnt the English Tongue” begging for Conway’s protection, given the affection that Conway has shown for the Spanish language.

After this, Vades-forte translates The Allowance of Melchor de Lara, reminding that Melchor de Lara is “Physitian Generall for the Kingdome of Spain”. This piece is followed by the Testimonial of John de Mena, “Doctor and Physitian to the King of Spain”. Finally, the section finishes with the proper preface, entitled “To the Reader”.

Regarding the treatise printed in 1562, on Wadsworth’s cover page, below the title, *Chocolate, or an Indian Drinke*, the reader finds a lengthy explanation on the virtues of chocolate that Albala considers that it “will give some indication of how chocolate came to be advertised” (2007: 69): “By the wise and Moderate use

whereof, Health is preserved, Sicknesse Diverted, and Cured, especially the Plague of the Guts; vulgarly called *The New Disease*; Fluxes, Consumptions, & Coughs of the Lungs, with sundry other desperate Diseases. By it also, Conception is Caused, the Birth Hastened and facilitated, Beauty Gain'd and continued". As can be seen, this subtitle is not a direct translation of Colmenero's subtitle, but a praise for the benefits of chocolate.

The prefatory items in this case include a letter "To the gentry of the English nation", signed by Diego de Vades-forte. Here Wadsworth admits that some years ago he translated the same treatise and dedicated it to the Honourable Edward Lord Conway under whose patronage the drink was introduced into the English court. According to Wadsworth, since then, chocolate has been much sought especially by the female sex. He continues referring to the etymological origin of the word *chocolate* and enumerates the virtues of the beverage, some of which were not present in the original Spanish text:

It preserves Health, and makes such as drink it often, Fat, and Corpulent, faire and Amiable, it vehemently Incites to *Venus*, and causeth Conception in women, hastens and facilitates their Delivery: It is an excellent help to Digestion, it cures Consumptions, and the Cough of the Lungs, the New Disease, or Plague of the Guts, and other Fluxes, the Green Sicknesse, Jaundise, and all manner of Inflammations, Opilations, and Obstructions. It quite takes away the Morpew, Cleanseth the Teeth, and sweetneth the Breath, Provokes Urine, Cures the Stone, and strangury, Expells Poison, and preserves from all infectious Diseases (Wadsworth 1562: A4).

The English rendering now adds a section entitled "*THE TRANSLATOR*, To every Individuall Man, and Woman, Learn'd, or unlearn'd, Honest, or Dishonest: In the due Praise of Divine *CHOCOLATE*", which contains twenty-two satirical stanzas made up of four verses (rhyme scheme AABB) listing the qualities of chocolate. This composition is missing in the 1640 translation of the work.

Then comes The allowance of Melchor Lara, the Testimonial of John de Mena, a short piece aimed at the Author which reads: "Great Don, Grandee of *Spaine*, Illostrissimo of *Venice*, High and mighty King of *Candie*, Great Bashaw of *Babilon*, Prince of the Moone, Lord of the Seven Starres, Governour of the Castle of *Comfort*, Sole Admirall of the Floating *Caravan*, Author of *Th'Europian Mercury*, Chiefe Generall and Admirall of the Invisible Fleet and Army of *Terra Incognita*" and finally, the preface "To the Reader". Lastly, the four points, which work as chapters, are included and there is a final addition in this version on "How to make use of chocolate" and "The manner of making chocolate", where the use of a specific tool, *molinillo*, is needed to produce chocolate³.

³ A drawing of this *molinillo* is found in a recipe for chocolate in English, recorded in Lady Fanshawe's manuscript (Wellcome MS 7113: 332). Lady Fanshawe lived in Spain in 1650 and returned to Britain in 1651, when she began the compilation of her recipe book (Davidson 2004). This is one of the earliest English manuscript recipes including chocolate. Soon after, the first Earl of Sandwich

METHODOLOGY

For the comparison of the texts, digital copies have been used: Colmenero's *Curioso Tratado de la Naturaleza y Calidad del Chocolate* (1631) is available through the website of the Biblioteca Nacional de Madrid and, in the case of *A Curious Treatise of the Nature and Quality of Chocolate* (1640) and *Chocolate, or an Indian Drinke* (1652), both have been retrieved from *Early English Books Online*. I have read through the texts and contrasted both the original and the target work. By doing so, I have concentrated on the analysis of the translation strategies used by Wadsworth in his rendering of the Spanish treatise tagging them according to the selected theoretical method.

I have considered several well-known taxonomies laid out by Vinay and Darbelnet (1958/1995), Vázquez-Ayora (1977), Newmark (1988), Chesterman (1997), Molina and Hurtado-Albir (2002) and Gil-Bardaji (2009). I have finally decided to adopt the framework proposed by Cruz-García (2013) and adapted by Alonso-Almeida and Sánchez (2016), because Cruz-García's proposal has grown from the examination of previous models in the analysis of translation techniques and the adaptation by Alonso-Almeida and Sánchez seems to serve the purpose of dealing with a historical text. Based on several of the abovementioned scholars and others, such as Cómite-Narváez (1999) and Valdés-Rodríguez (2004), Cruz-García divides the techniques into two main groups, namely *translation methods*, and *translation procedures*, following Newmark (1988).

TRANSLATION METHODS

Translation methods operate at the macrostructure level and include: (1) foreignisation, (2) literal translation, (3) adaptation and (4) creation. In *foreignisation*, there is no translation of the text. Vinay and Darbelnet already noted that "to overcome a lacuna, usually a metalinguistic one (e.g. a new technical process, an unknown concept), borrowing is the simplest of all translation methods" (1995: 31). As for *literal translation*, this is closely associated with the inequivalence of the languages, inasmuch as the length and structure of the source text are kept in the target text along with the contents. The third method was already named *adaptation* by Vinay and Darbelnet, whereby it is "used in those cases where the type of situation being referred to by the SL message is unknown in the TL culture (or the referent has an undesirable connotation)" (1995: 39). This implies that culturally motivated aspects are replaced by their equivalents in the target culture or are omitted completely, if

referred above, who succeeded Lady Fanshawe's husband as Ambassador to Spain, will provide another recipe in his journal in 1668 (Loveman 2013: 27).

considered unimportant or meaningless in the target language. The last method on the list, *creation*, is that whose primary aim is to offer a new text “with an equivalent pragmatic effect to that of the ST in the SC” (Cruz-García 2013: 354).

TRANSLATION PROCEDURES

Unlike the previous methods, translation procedures “are applicable at a micro-textual level to specific elements within the text” (Cruz-García 2013: 354). They include amplification, explicitation, omission, modulation, equivalence, and compensation. Besides, Cruz-García supplements the list including several additional strategies: addition, condensation, partial foreignisation, partial adaptation and partial creation.

Alonso-Almeida and Sánchez (2016), based on Cruz-García’s classification, have grouped the translation procedures into a) reduction, b) extension, c) focalisation, d) substitution and e) non-translation. Thus, the eleven categories established by Cruz-García have been organised into five. I have followed this taxonomy closely, since it seems to be more operative than other classifications dealing with such large number of techniques. The definition of each technique can be consulted in Table 1:

Table 1. Translation procedures (adapted from Alonso-Almeida, Sánchez 2016: 47)

Group	Procedure	Definition
Reduction	Omission Condensation	A portion of text is not included in TT. The translator uses a shorter number of morphemes in the TT.
Extension	Addition Explicitation Amplification	This involves the inclusion of new material absent in the ST. Implicit information is written out in the TT. The translator uses a larger number of morphemes in the TT.
Focalisation	Modulation Compensation	This procedure indicates ‘a change in perspective or emphasis with regard to the ST’. An expression of the ST is expressed in a different place in the TT.
Substitution	Partial creation Partial adaptation Equivalence	A new element is created in the TT to replace another one with different meaning in the ST. A ST cultural-specific element is replaced in the TT with a cultural-specific element of the TC. This indicates the use of an expression in the TT, which is pragmatically similar but differs in form and meaning.

Table 1 cont.

Group	Procedure	Definition
	Third language foreignisation	The use of a third language different to the source language and to the target language.
	Another language	The use of a foreign language in the source text is replaced by the use of the target language.
Non-translation	Partial foreignisation	Some original language of the ST remains in the TT.

As in the case of the analysis by Alonso-Almeida and Sánchez, the translation procedures in my corpus fit nicely into the above categories. Furthermore, although based on Cruz-García (2013), these authors add another substitution procedure *partial third language foreignisation*: “It refers to the use of a third language different to the source language and to the target language” (Alonso-Almeida, Sánchez 2016: 46). This has proved productive in the translation of Colmenero’s Spanish text into English, as will be shown in the next section. Subsequently, this substitution technique has been introduced in the division of translation strategies. Likewise, a new technique is documented in the English rendering of Colmenero’s text. I have labelled it *another language*, which implies “the use of a foreign language in the source text is replaced by the use of the target language”. This procedure did not occur in any of the revised classifications but happens once in Wadsworth’s text. All these additions are shown in Table 1.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In his attempt to make culture-specific items understood in the target culture, Wadsworth resorted to diverse strategies, like other scholars had done before in their translations of new realities from the New World⁴. It is difficult to quantify the exact number of techniques used by the translator. On the one hand, in one sentence several strategies may co-occur, and, on the other hand, the same strategy may be repeated numerous times through the text. Thus, my focus is chiefly on the qualitative interpretation of the data, rather than on the quantitative approach.

All in all, most translation actions have to do with non-translation procedures. In fact, every time there is a new product the original Indian American word, which was not translated into Spanish either, is preserved. Thus, eventually many of this kind of lexical units will remain in the language. Other common strategies are the extension procedures, specifically (addition, explicitation and amplification), as well as substitution, while focalisation (modulation and compensation) is only sparingly

⁴ See for instance, Ríos-Castaño (2015) on Sahagun’s sixteenth-century techniques from Nahuatl into Spanish.

deployed. Reduction (omission and condensation) is not so frequently found either. I will subsequently comment on all these categories. All samples in the analysis reflect original spelling and punctuation.

REDUCTION

This group includes the categories of omission and condensation. The translator avoids mentioning certain aspects of the original in the target text. Thus, in the examples below the words or expressions in bold are not rendered in English:

- (1) ST: y de la primera de Galeno lib.3 de la facultad de los **medicamentos** simples (Colmenero 1631: 2–3).
TT: and let the first be from *Gallen*, l.3. Of the qualities of Simples (Wadsworth 1652: 8).
- (2) ST: Y la sustancia del suero purgatiua, como consta del mismo Galeno **Lib. de la facultad de los mantenimientos**, cap. 15 (Colmenero 1631: 3).
TT: And the substance of Whay, which is purging; and Butter, as it is expressed in the said *Gallen*, *Cap. 15* (Wadsworth 1652: 10).
- (3) ST: Los otros se llaman Chilpatlagua, que son vnos **chiles, ò pimientos** mui anchos (Colmenero 1631: 6).
TT: The other Pepper is called Chilpaclagua, which hath a broad huske (Wadsworth 1652: 21).
- (4) ST: Polues de **rosas de** Alexandria (Colmenero 1631: 6b).
TT: Powder of *Alexandria* (Wadsworth 1652: 22).
- (5) ST: Se puede añadir pepitas de melon, **de calabaza**, y de valenzia (Colmenero 1631: 11–11b).
TT: You may adde Mellon-seeds, and seeds of Pompions of *Valencia* (Wadsworth 1652: 40).

The reason for the omission could be that Wadsworth did not consider that information to be relevant to his readers or that so much information on specific products would be unnecessary.

EXTENSION

Regarding this type of techniques, it is worth mentioning the fact that several instances of sentences in Latin in the source text are reproduced with no translation into Spanish. However, in the English version, the Latin text is followed directly by

- (12) ST: Dentro de vna calabacilla, tan grande como vna breua (Colmenero 1631: 4).
 TT: In one Gorde or Cod, which is of the bignesse of a greate black Figge (Wadsworth 1652: 14).
- (13) ST: Las vainillas de Campeche son mui lindas (Colmenero 1631: 5).
 TT: The Huskes or Cods of Logwood, or *Campeche* are very good (Wadsworth 1652: 17).

Wadsworth does not use the word *vanilla* in example (13), since, according to the *Oxford English Dictionary*, it was first recorded in the language in another treatise on chocolate, *The Indian Nectar*, by Stubbe (1662). Regarding *Campeche*, it was first documented in the English language in Wadsworth's translation (1652) according to the *Oxford English Dictionary*.

Sometimes the expansion is due to proper linguistic reasons. Thus, whereas in Spanish there is only one word to mean *açahar*, in English, two words are needed: *orange flowers*. Similarly, *açogue* is rendered as *quick-silver*. Although used in special contexts, in Spanish *azogue* is a synonym for *mercury*, which appears translated as *quick-silver* in contemporary specialised works. Thus, in the translation of Alonso Barba's *El arte de los metales*, published in Spanish in 1640 and translated into English in 1674 by the first Earl of Sandwich, *azogue* is systematically rendered as *quick-silver*⁵.

FOCALISATION

This group of techniques, which comprise modulation and compensation, is not frequently found in the English version. Modulation implies a change in perspective, while compensation indicates a change resulting in a different wording of the source text in the translated material. The latter seeks to maintain the effect of the source text in the target text. Examples of focalisation are the following:

- (14) ST: El Cacao, y los demas ingredientes, se muelen en vna piedra, que llaman Metate, hecha para el proposito (Colmenero 1631: 8b).
 TT: The Cacao, and the other Ingredients must be beaten in a Morter of Stone, or ground upon a broad stone, which the Indians call Metate, and is onely made for that use (Wadsworth 1652: 30).
- (15) ST: La flor a la que llamamos espuma (Colmenero 1631: 3).
 TT: Which is the flower, and may be called the scum, or froath (Wadsworth 1652: 10).

Whereas the verbs in Spanish are in present tense indicative describing the manner in which its ingredients are processed (*se muelen*), and the fact that they are

⁵ For the translation techniques used in this specific work, see De la Cruz-Cabanillas (2018).

called *scum* (*llamamos espuma*), in English they report either an obligation with the use of *must* or a possibility by means of *may*.

Other changes have to do with the syntactical structures used to render the original text, as well as the order of the elements. Thus, in Spanish a relative clause introduced by *quien* is replaced for the purpose by means of the preposition *for* and the gerund in English:

(16) ST: Y en lugar deste en España se puede mezclar en la pasta, quien tuuiere necesidad de alargar el vientre, polues de rosas de Alexandria (Colmenero 1631: 6–6b).

TT: Instead of this, in *Spaine* they put into the *Confection*, powder of *Alexandria*, for opening the Belly (Wadsworth 1652: 22).

SUBSTITUTION

Within the substitution procedures in the translation of Colmenero's treatise in English, the *partial third language foreignisation* technique is worth mentioning. Thus, several expressions that in the source text are in Spanish are rendered in Latin in the English version:

(17) ST: Dos calidades contrarias y disimbolas, no pueden estar en gradu intenso en vn sujeto (Colmenero 1631: 2).

TT: Two contrary Qualities, and Disagreeing, cannot be in gradu intenso, in one and the same subject (Wadsworth 1652: 6).

(18) ST: Por parecerle contra Filosofia el hallarse en el calor y humedad en gradu intenso (Colmenero 1631: 2).

TT: It seeming to be contrary to Philosophy, that in it there should be found Heat and Moysture, in gradu intenso (Wadsworth 1652: 6).

Related to this technique, the opposite procedure is observed when the use of a foreign language in the source text "Modus facendi" is replaced by the use of the target language "The way of Compounding" (Wadsworth 1562: 30).

It is also remarkable the equivalence found in English by Wadsworth reproducing a phraseological unit in Spanish: "con esta horma no se pueden calçar todos los sujetos" (Colmenero 1631: 4b) with "This shooe will not fit every foot" (Wadsworth 1562: 15). This device is geared at getting the same pragmatical force conveyed by the phraseological unit in the source text.

Finally, as a partly adapted device, Wadsworth modifies the original to a great extent with the objective of enabling his target audience to understand the system of measures and the currencies of seventeenth-century Spain. Thus, *reales* and shillings are combined in the translation, and *fanegas* and other measures as well:

- (19) ST: anis peso de dos reales; (Colmenero 1631: 4b).
 TT: the weight of 2. Reals, or a shilling of Anniseeds (Wadsworth 1562: 15).
- (20) ST: Costandoles cada fanega de maiz diez y seis reales, les sale vendido cada libra por ocho, que es el precio que vale cada libra dèl (Colmenero 1631: 5b).
 TT: Every *Fanega* or measure of *Grani* containing a Bushell and a halfe, is sold for eight shillings, and they sell this confection for foure shillings a pound, which is the ordinary price of Chocolate (Wadsworth 1562: 20).

In this sense, when Wadsworth encounters specific words that will not be understood by his audience, he opts out for substituting the term with a more familiar one. Thus, *jícara* is a very technical word defined as “a small, generally ceramic vessel, which is usually employed to drink chocolate”⁶. He replaces this technicism with *draught*, which means “A quantity drawn: used as a specific measure of something drawn, extracted, or taken up” (*Oxford English Dictionary*).

NON-TRANSLATION

Despite the use of all the other procedures, the most salient feature in the English version is the partial foreignisation, which implies that some parts of the original language of the source text remain in the target text. Given the nature of the treatise, there are culture-specific items which are defined as “the result of a conflict arising from any linguistic represented reference in a source text when, transferred to a target language, poses a translation problem due to the nonexistence or to the different value (whether determined by ideology, usage, frequency, etc.) of the given items in the target language culture” (Franco-Aixelá 1996: 57).

In this case, these culture-specific items are products discovered in the Americas. Most plant names are taken from indigenous languages, which explains why this technique is so prominent in both the source and the target text. Thus, every time a new item appears, the original indigenous language is preserved. This is the case of *chocolate*, *cacao*, *achiote/agiote*, *criollas*, *Patlaxte*, etc. Often the lexical units are very technical, as when enumerating the different varieties of long red pepper: *Chilchotes*, *Chilterpin*, *Tonalchiles* and *Chilpaclagua*.

One is called *Chilchotes*: the other very little, which they call *Chilterpin*; and these two kinds, are very quicke and biting. The other two are called *Tonalchiles*, and these are moderately hot; for they are eaten with bread, as they eate other fruits, & they are of a yellow colour; and they grow onely about the Townes, which are in, and adjoyning to the Lake of *Mexico*. The other Pepper is called *Chilpaclagua*, which hath a broad huske, and this is not so biting as the

⁶ Author’s translation of “Vasija pequeña, generalmente de loza, que suele emplearse para tomar chocolate” (*Diccionario de la Lengua Española*).

first; nor so gentle as the last, and is that, which is usually put into the *Chocolate* (Wadsworth 1652: 21).

Likewise, many other technicisms are introduced as such, with no further explanation or synonym. For instance, *Orejuelas*, *Vinacaxlidos*, *Mechasuchil*, *Atolle* and *tausco*. In fact, the *Oxford English Dictionary* documents Wadsworth's translation as the first quotation of the word *tabasco* in the English language. As can be seen, the foreign character of the borrowing is marked using italics in the English version. The conservation process may involve the orthographical adaptation of the word. Thus, at the time <ç> was in use in Spanish, but Wadsworth anglicises this into <s> Subsequently, "el maiz, ò paniço" is rendered as "*Maiz*, or *Paniso*".

CONCLUSIONS

The *Curioso Tratado de la Naturaleza y Calidad del Chocolate* by Antonio Colmenero de Ledesma was one of the first treatises devoted exclusively to the medical properties of chocolate. It gained wide recognition thanks to the translations in other languages. Among them, the English version by Wadsworth, educated as a child in Spain and, therefore, connoisseur of the Spanish language and culture, is particularly important. This article concentrates on the translation choices and strategies deployed by him as a translator.

The analysis of the texts reveals that the conservation of original forms is a widely used procedure in the rendition of the Spanish text into English. The function of this strategy is to introduce newly discovered items in the New World to an English audience. In fact, some of these lexical units like *tabasco* and *campeche* are regarded the first English record of the word in the *Oxford English Dictionary*. Having no previous reference in the target language, the translator chooses to reproduce these culture-specific items in their original forms or with very little adaptation.

Similarly, extension strategies are aimed at producing effective communication. Wadsworth uses extension mainly to clarify the technical or unfamiliar words, as well as to make Latin extracts understandable to an English audience. This goal is also achieved with reduction techniques, which means that some parts from the source text are not translated, when the translator considers that the information is not relevant to his audience.

Within the other devices, substitution is also attested, especially by adapting units of measure and currencies, while focalisation is employed to a lesser degree. The use of the different techniques is geared at making the text accessible to a society increasingly interested in the consumption of chocolate, its medical properties and the way of production and preparation.

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